

Kinetics and Mechanism of Os(VIII) Catalysed Oxidation of Methyl Phenyl Sulphoxide by Chloramine-T

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The Os(VIII) catalysed oxidation of methyl phenyl sulphoxide by chloramine-T (CAT) in the presence of sodium hydroxide has been studied. *t*-Butanol-water mixture (1 : 1 v/v) is used as solvent. The reaction shows first order in each CAT and OsO₄. The order with respect to the sulphoxide is found to be 0.5. A suitable mechanism taking CAT as the reactive species is proposed.

THE oxidation of methyl phenyl sulphoxide by chloramine-T (CAT) in the presence of hydrochloric acid^{1,2} was studied and the mechanism was explained by taking HOCl as the oxidising species. In buffered ethanol-water³ a mixed order rate law was obtained. With a view to understand the mechanism of the reaction in alkaline medium, the reaction was carried out in the presence of sodium hydroxide. OsO₄ was used as catalyst.

Experimental

Methyl phenyl sulphoxide was prepared by the usual method and the purity was checked by tlc. Chloramine-T was prepared and was freed from dichloro-contaminant by washing several times with carbon tetrachloride. The kinetics was followed by estimating the unreacted chloramine-T iodometrically.

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometry of the reaction was found to be 1 : 1 corresponding to the following equation

The product was identified as methyl phenyl sulphone from its melting point and the mixed melting point with an authentic sample.

The oxidation was studied over a wide range of concentrations of reactants (Table 1). The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_1) calculated in CAT at different initial concentrations are independent of the oxidant concentration. A variation in the substrate concentration showed a fractional order (0.5) dependence (Table 1). The variation in sodium hydroxide concentration and the ionic strength has no effect on the reaction rate (Tables 2 and 3). The rate of oxidation was found to vary with the concentration of OsO₄ (Table 4). The activation parameters namely the energy, enthalpy, entropy

and the free energy of activation were found to be 33.77 kJ mol⁻¹, 31.25 kJ mol⁻¹, -185.20 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ and 87.36 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING THE CONCENTRATION OF THE REACTANTS

Temp., 35°; [NaOH] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ M; [OsO₄] = 2.0 × 10⁻⁴ M

[CAT] M	[C ₆ H ₅ SOCH ₃] M	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	k _{1, s} × 10 ⁴ lit ^{1/2} mol ^{-1/2} sec ⁻¹
0.0010	0.030	12.56	—
0.0015	0.030	12.64	—
0.0020	0.030	12.23	—
0.0025	0.030	12.31	—
0.0020	0.010	7.086	7.086
0.0020	0.015	8.924	7.286
0.0020	0.020	10.130	7.161
0.0020	0.040	14.500	7.251
0.0020	0.060	17.410	7.115

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING HYDROXIDE ION CONCENTRATION

Temp., 35°; [C₆H₅SOCH₃] = 3.0 × 10⁻³ M;
[CAT] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ M; [OsO₄] = 2.0 × 10⁻⁴ M

[OH ⁻] M	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹
0.0020	1.223
0.0025	1.205
0.0030	1.230
0.0035	1.196
0.0040	1.171

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARYING IONIC STRENGTH

Temp., 35°; [C₆H₅SOCH₃] = 3.0 × 10⁻³ M;
[CAT] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ M; [NaOH] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ M;
[OsO₄] = 2.0 × 10⁻⁴ M

I M	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹
0.10	1.842
0.20	1.850
0.30	1.802
0.40	1.804

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF VARYING THE CONCENTRATION OF OsO₄

Temp., 35°; [C₆H₅SOCH₃]=3.0×10⁻³ M;
[CAT]=2.0×10⁻³ M; [NaOH]=2.0×10⁻³ M

[OsO ₄] × 10 ⁵ M	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	$\frac{k_1}{[\text{OsO}_4]}$ l mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
2.5	1.466	5.865
5.0	3.027	6.063
10.0	6.117	6.117
15.0	9.596	6.397
20.0	12.230	6.115

The possible oxidising species in alkaline medium are CAT, RNHCl, HOCl, ClO⁻ and RNCl₂. In an alkaline medium the concentrations of RNCl₂ and HOCl are very low^{4,5}. This observation along with the first order dependence on CAT ruled out the possibilities of either RNCl₂ or HOCl being the oxidising species. If RNHCl were the reactive species, then retardation by OH⁻ must be observed. In strongly alkaline medium only ClO⁻ predominates⁴. Hence, it is concluded that the only oxidising species possible in this reaction condition is chloramine-T. The following mechanism is proposed.

Fig. 1. Plot of $\frac{1}{\text{Rate}} \times 10^{-2}$ vs $\frac{1}{[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{SOCH}_3]}$.

If the step (1) is the only rate-determining reaction, then the rate must be independent of the substrate concentration. Similarly, if the step (2) is the only rate-determining reaction, then the reaction would predict a first order dependence on the substrate concentration. The step (3) as rate-determining is also ruled out as it would also predict a first order dependence. But a fractional order (0.5) dependence is observed. Hence, simultaneous formation of the intermediate (I) and its interaction with the sulphoxide are considered as rate-determining steps. This is evidenced by the Michaelis plot (Fig. 1) corresponding to the equation (4).

Applying steady-state concept,

$$\frac{1}{\text{Rate}} = \frac{k_{-1} + k_3 [\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{SOCH}_3]}{k_1 k_2 [\text{RNCl}^-] [\text{OsO}_4] [\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{SOCH}_3]}$$

$$\frac{1}{\text{Rate}} = \frac{k_4}{[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{SOCH}_3]} + k_3 \quad \dots (4)$$

where, $k_4 = \frac{k_{-1}}{k_1 k_2 [\text{RNCl}^-] [\text{OsO}_4]}$

and $k_3 = \frac{1}{k_1 [\text{RNCl}^-] [\text{OsO}_4]}$

The formation of the following cyclic complex is assumed. The cyclic structure indicates that the

electron density of nitrogen is decreased weakening N-Cl bond. Therefore the interaction with the substrate is increased.

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